

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Volunteer Activities in the Italian Regions during the Period 2005 and 2022

They decreased on average by 7.54%

Istat calculates the value of volunteer activities. The variable is defined as people aged 14 and over who have carried out free activities for associations or voluntary groups in the last 12 months out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2005 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of voluntary activities in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of voluntary activities with an amount of 17.00, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 12.6 and from Lombardy with an amount of 108.8 units. In the middle of the table are Abruzzo with a value of 8.5 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 8.2 units and Lazio with a value of 7.8 units. Molise closes the ranking with an amount of 5.1 units, followed by Puglia with an amount of 4.9 units, and Sicily with a value of 4.8 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in voluntary activities between 2005 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place by value of the percentage change in voluntary activities between 2005 and 2022 with an amount equal to 18.06 % corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.20 units up to 8.50 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to an amount of 17.46% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.30 units up to a value of 7.40 units. Campania follows with a value of 17.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.20 units up to an amount of 6.10 units. In the middle of the table are Calabria with a variation equal to an amount of -5.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.60 units in 2005 up to an amount of 5.30 units in 2022. Umbria follows. with a value equal to -5.56% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.20 units up to 6.80 units between 2005 and 2022. Below is Lombardy with a variation equal to an amount of -6, 09% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.50 units up to an amount of 10.80 units. In the last places Trentino Alto Adige with a variation equal to an amount of -23.42% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.20 units in 2005 up to a value of 27.00 units in 2022. Veneto follows with a value equal to -29.20% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 13.70 units in 2005 up to an amount of 9.70 units in 2022. The Marche region is in last place with a value equal to -33, 64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.00 units in 2005 up to an amount of 7.30 units in 2022. Between 2005 and 2022 the average value of voluntary activity in the Italian regions decreased by -7 .54% going from an amount of 9.02 units up to a value of 8.34 units.

Volunteering activities in the Italian regions between 2005 and 2022. The value of volunteering activities in the Italian regions between 2005 and 2002 decreased in almost all Italian macro-regions. Particularly in the North with -10.53%, North-West with -1.92%, North-East with -20.93%, Center with -2.44%, Southern Italy with -1.69%, Islands with -10.00%. The value of voluntary activity in

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it , Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

the South grew by 3.45% between 2005 and 2022. However, even if the value of voluntary activity has decreased in almost all macro-regions, it is also true that a divergence remains between the regions of the Centre-North, with medium-high levels of volunteering activity, and the southern regions, with medium-low levels of volunteering. For example, volunteering activity in Southern Italy is 41% lower than in Northern Italy, 41% lower than in the North-West, 41% lower than in the North-East and 25% lower than in the Centre.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Lazio, Puglia, Calabria, Abruzzo, Molise, Sicily, Campania, Sardinia, Liguria, Umbria, Marche, Tuscany;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta, Emilia Romagna, Piedmont.

We can see that by calculating the average value of the clusters it turns out that the value of cluster 2 is dominant compared to the value of cluster 1, so $C2 > C1$. Cluster 2, i.e. the cluster made up of the regions that have high volunteering values, essentially refers to the regions of the North-East and North-West. In cluster 2 both the northern regions and the regions of Central Italy are absent. Cluster 1 is instead made up of the southern and central Italian regions with the sole exception of Liguria. In fact, Liguria, despite being a region of the North-West, is assimilated to the central-southern regions in terms of the value of voluntary activities.

Conclusions. Volunteering activities decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022 with the sole exception of Southern Italy, where there was a marginal growth amounting to 3.45%. Despite the generalized reduction in the value of volunteering activity in the Italian regions, significant differences persist between the southern regions, with medium-low levels, and the regions of Central-Northern Italy with medium-high levels. From a socio-cultural and religious point of view we can note that the regions of Southern Italy, where there is generally greater religious faith and a greater culture of hospitality, record much lower levels of volunteering compared to the regions of Central-Northern Italy which instead they appear more secular and oriented towards an individualistic culture. Furthermore, it is possible to note that the regions that have higher per capita income are also the regions that have higher levels of voluntary activity compared to the regions that have lower per capita incomes. That is, the data highlights, even in the general decline of the variable, that voluntary activities grow in regions characterized by greater secularization, income availability, civil and political freedom, and cultural emancipation.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

